

Corporate Social Responsibility: Study of the Perception of Agricultural Managers in Cameroon

Responsabilité Sociale Des Entreprises : Etude De La Perception Des Dirigeants D'exploitations Agricoles Au Cameroun

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Abstract: The objective of this article is to understand the perception of farm managers of CSR. To achieve this, we mobilized a qualitative research, more precisely an empirical survey of exploratory type based on case studies with 13 leaders of large, small and medium farms in Cameroon. The discourse of the actors allowed us to identify 4 types of leaders: 7 pragmatic leaders who have a good knowledge of CSR and implement it with full knowledge of the facts; 2 lay leaders who have no knowledge of CSR and therefore do not apply it; 3 of the respondents are altruistic and therefore have no knowledge of CSR but apply it without knowing it; Finally, we found in terms of discourse, 1 deviant leader who has a good knowledge of CSR, but does not apply it. The social component of CSR is the most familiar to farm managers. We recommend that managers get in touch with competent experts in the field or with the ministry in charge, which will be of great help to them in mastering the techniques that can help them make good use of CSR for a better future of their farms. We encourage public authorities to set up incentives to encourage companies, especially small ones (more numerous), to adopt responsible behaviors. Training programs for managers wishing to learn about CSR would be welcome, especially in the vernacular language of community radio stations, to help managers who do not easily use French and English to grasp the concept.

Key words: " CSR; CSR perception; farm; Cameroon."

I. Introduction

"A company must make a profit, or it will die. But if you try to run a business on profit alone, then it will also die because it will have no reason to exist. Henri Ford, (1920). This quote from an eminent industrialist makes us think about the real missions of a company worthy of the name. It brings to light the environmental and social problems encountered in companies and more specifically the plantations in the depths of Africa, South America or elsewhere, where some of the food we consume on a daily basis or the raw materials used to manufacture many basic products come from. Here the economic, social and environmental sorting resurfaces, reminiscent of Elkington's (1994) relating to CSR, which was first put on the spot in 1953 in the book by its founding father, Howard Bowen, "the social responsibility of businessmen".

The ISO 26000 standard, among other definitions, defines a responsible company as one that contributes to sustainable development, including the health and well-being of society. Although a late adopter of this concept in Africa, several authors have devoted research to it (Sogbossi Bocco, 2010; Ondoia biwolé, 2012; Wong and Yaméogo, 2011; Lado, Ambassa, Ngnodjom and Nkoulou, 2012, 2014; Pigé and Bogou-Laré, 2015; Moskolai, 2016; Ngok evina, 2017; Etogo, 2019); Diop Sall et al, 2019). Sangué Fotso, (2018) explains that a responsible company is one that voluntarily or involuntarily contributes to the well-being of its staff and society.

The term CSR is now part of the common vocabulary of the business world. It is used in several ways. On almost every continent, its implementation in companies is becoming unavoidable. On a global level and especially in developed countries, CSR has proven to be a source of competitive advantage for companies. The application of its principles in the global strategy of companies has produced admirable results. These responsible companies offer real prospects for the future and are as good as the high potential companies. The leaders of companies in the South would have a great interest in really adopting it to try to find its marks with its "congeners" elsewhere. These responsible companies will thus participate in the improvement of the economies of their continent. Only, to implement CSR, it is necessary to know it and its principles.

The agricultural sector plays a major role in the world's economic success. It is the lifeblood of humanity. It employs more than 40 percent of the world's workforce. Agriculture offers wonderful prospects for the future that could benefit countries in the South like Cameroon: The non-food valuations of products or by-products of agriculture, in particular to generate agrofuels, with a view to developing renewable energy. This is particularly true for second generation agrofuels (from whole plants or green residues...) which are less competitive with food crops. To achieve this, a deep reflection in upstream allows the implementation of strategies that can lead to the economic explosion of this sector with great potential. Among these strategies, CSR has a prominent place.

On farms, the persistence of CSR issues is increasing, due to certain realities that are obvious to the first visitor. On site visits to several large farms, one can see workers who have worked or are working on these plantations. Old retirees with more than 20 years of loyal service, some suffering from various ailments related to the hardship of work, others, blind abandoned to their sad fate and accusing the effect of toxic chemicals used during their years of service. Others, sitting in front of hovels built with local materials, especially wood waste, serving as their home; a great ambient poverty is noticeable and confirmed by their statement. Most of their children, who have not completed their schooling due to lack of money, are preparing to join the future employees of the only source of income for miles around, the "farm of death" as the parents call it.

The young people we met said they were working there for lack of anything better. Most of them do not have the possibility to build a house and still live in the family house, unable for many of them to build a family worthy of the name. Almost all of them speak the same language: miserable wages, too many broken promises, bad working conditions...etc. Another reality is the spraying of the plantations with chemicals by small planes. Inhabitants, rivers, houses and even hospitals are sprayed as they pass.

The camps where the employees live look like snake dens. The hydrants, or what remains of them, have been out of order for several years without anyone being bothered. The employees in sandals, without helmets and without gloves run every step of the way in the plantations to receive a leg of walnuts on the head. Child labor is commonplace. Many people think critically and contemptuously about the agricultural sector. Many prefer to work in the agricultural sector as a "lowly" civil servant. Others consider this activity as a source of savings that will help them to embark on a perilous and uncertain adventure to the West, a source of well-being. Unfortunately, for many, this journey ends in the desert or in the Mediterranean. CSR seems to be merely cosmetic (Martinet and Payaux, 2008).

CSR, reality or chimera for stakeholders? The confrontation between the classical school and the proponents of stakeholder theory poses a serious problem of profit orientation. For the former, profit is the property of shareholders, the only investors, while the latter think of all the people and organizations that contribute to the creation of added value. According to the strategy of the top management of the company, the managers of the operations align themselves with a current of thought according to the representation they have of CSR. Depending on their perception of this concept, managers may or may not respect CSR standards. Thus, the representation of CSR by the manager becomes a key strategic factor. This leads us to ask the central question of this study: What is the perception of CSR by farm managers in Cameroon? The main objective of this study is to understand the perception of farm managers in terms of CSR. This research is articulated in two sections: the first deals with the CSR perception of leaders: a review of the literature while the second focuses on a qualitative exploratory study of the perception of leaders of 13 farms in Cameroon.

1.1- The CSR perception of managers: a review of the literature

Perception is based on cognition. Cognition is increasingly recognized in research on organizations (Cossette, 2008). It is important to know what it is. "Cognition is related to thought or knowledge. Most often, it refers to a particular function that is associated with activities or processes related to human intelligence. Generally speaking, the study of cognition concerns the processing of information and the knowledge that enables or results from it" Cossette (2008, p.3). If this is

the case, cognition, whether taken at the individual (managerial), or collective (organizational) level, allows for a better understanding of the process of formulating one's strategy. It can also help to better define other organizational behaviors such as performance and change. At the individual level, it is mainly interested in the decision-making process. (Schneider and Angelmar, 1993)

Codol(1989,p.474) defines cognition as "The set of activities by which all the information that the individual receives is processed by a psychic apparatus:How he receives it, how he selects it, how he transforms and organizes it, and how he thus constructs representations of reality and elaborates knowledge."

The perception of CSR is a topic of increasing interest to management science researchers (Adaskou, 2014; Moskolai et al, 2016; Stephano vacher et Al, 2016; Fotso Sangue, 2018). Many of these studies focus on SMEs; this is self-evident, as large companies have appropriated the concept of CSR either voluntarily or through constraints. It emerges from both qualitative and quantitative studies, mainly in SMEs, that some business leaders have no idea what CSR is. Others, on the other hand, are familiar with CSR to a certain extent or even extensively. These contradictory results, require in view of a clarification of further studies, to take into account the specificities of the sectors of activity (Moskolai et al, 2016 ;)

Managers of companies, both large and small, have a significant influence on strategic decision-making. It is therefore important to conduct studies to better understand the perception of these men on CSR. Knowledge of this perception will help ensure that the CSR actions that are implemented are a springboard for conducting other studies in the continuity for a better integration of this concept in various sectors of activity in Cameroon for a better competitiveness.

We will conduct a study on the perception of leaders in the agricultural sector. Before doing so, however, it will be useful to take stock of previous work on the perception of leaders in companies.

The literature is replete with divergent research results on the perception of managers of CSR. These results seem even more problematic when it comes to SMEs, given their specificities. The environment and the sector of activity in which the research is conducted seem to influence the results enormously. In recent years, Africa has become more interested in CSR research (Sogbossi Bocco, 2010; Ondoa biwolé, 2012; Wong and Yaméogo, 2011; Lado,Ambassa,Ngnodjom and Nkoulou, 2012; Sangué Fotso,2014 ,2018; Pigé and Bogou-Laré, 2015; Moskolai, 2016; Ngok evina, 2017; Etogo, 2019) ; Diop Sall et al, 2019) .

We summarize in the following table some of the results of work conducted by researchers on this issue.

Table1: Results of studies on the perception of CSR by business leaders

Hamidi Youcef(2014)	La Perception de la RSE chez les dirigeants d'entreprises Algériennes. Quelle forme ? Implicite ou explicite ?	237 Algerian SMEs Results: Managers engage in CSR behavior in their strategy without any full knowledge of it
Sangue Fotso,Robert (2018)	Perception de la RSE par les dirigeants des PME Camerounaises	Exploratory qualitative survey of 22 SME managers in Cameroon Result: SMEs have a non-exclusively lucrative purpose, that managerial convictions base the perception of CSR of SME managers on the maximization of their personal utility function and rely on CSR as a lever for maximizing this function and not as a purpose that is oriented towards seeking the general interest of all stakeholders. The perception of CSR depends on the sector of activity. Almost all SMEs have not formalized CSR.
Moskolai (2016)	La RSE au Cameroun : Miroir aux alouettes ou évidence ?	Quantitative study of 96 companies. Result: 82% have heard of CSR. 78% can give a definition, 11.5% could not say what their perception of CSR is, let alone the general usefulness that taking it into account could bring to the company. 68% have really integrated CSR into their daily management.

Leila Ben Hassine et Chiraz Ghozzi-Nekheli(2013)	Perception de la RSE par leurs dirigeants : une comparaison entre PME tunisienne certifiées et non certifiées	Qualitative study with 8 Tunisian SMEs Result: Weak distinction between the certified and non-certified as to the appropriation of the concept of CSR and the identification of motivations and obstacles. Personal conviction and culture influence the commitment to CSR
Zouhair Laarraf(2010)	Analyse perceptuelle des déterminants de l'engagement sociétal des entreprises marocaines labellisées RSE : De la performance au développement durable	Qualitative and quantitative study of 60 companies. Result: Good knowledge of CSR. Commitment to CSR is a performance factor

Sources: Our care

2.1- Methodology of the exploratory study

In order to expose the methodology of the exploratory qualitative study that we carried out, we will first highlight the objectives of this study, then we will present the method of data collection used, and finally, we will explain the method of data analysis used in the framework of this study.

2.2- Objectives of the exploratory qualitative study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the perception of Cameroonian farmers of CSR. In other words, it is a question of trying to understand, through a qualitative study, the representation of CSR by farmers in Cameroon. Two cases are considered in this study for a better analysis and understanding of this perception. It is important to make a clear distinction between large farms and small and medium-sized farms. It is understood that, as with traditional enterprises, large enterprises and SMEs each have their own specificities, especially in terms of management. SMEs are influenced by their managers, who are generally the "alpha and omega" in terms of decision-making and management. Large companies are mostly branches of multinationals and are influenced by the strategic policies of their parent companies.

2.3- Method of data collection for the exploratory qualitative study

The first sub-section will be devoted to the data collection technique that we used in this research. The field of our investigation will be the subject of the second sub-section. The third section will deal with the selection of the sample. The fourth sub-section will focus on the data collection instrument that we used.

2.3.1- Data collection technique: individual semi-directive interview

Qualitative research uses several primary data collection methods: individual interviews, group interviews, and participant or non-participant observation (Thiéart et al., 2003).

In a research study, the choice of one data collection technique over another depends on the purpose of the study. The objective of our study is to explore how farmers in Cameroon represent CSR and what CSR practices are being implemented. Observations of farmers will not allow us to know what they think about or know about CSR. The perception of CSR is a psychological state and not a behavior or a behavioral intention. Therefore, only the farmers' discourse and therefore interviews with them can allow us to better understand their perception of the concept of CSR. In the context of this study, we chose the individual interview because this technique is recommended and appropriate when it comes to identifying appropriation logics, analyzing individual processes of attitude formation, or reporting on the validity of behaviors (Jolibert and Jourdan, 2006). In this study, given the objectives, we will be led to identify the appropriation logic of farm managers of CSR on the one hand, and report on the practices implemented as a result of this perception on the other.

After choosing the interview, we then had to select the type of interview to implement. Three possibilities were offered to us: The directive interview, the semi-directive interview, and the non-directive interview. In the directive interview, the researcher directs the interview by asking questions (Fenneteau, 2007). Each question invites the interviewee to develop a mini discourse (Fenneteau, 2007), which reduces the richness of the information collected. In a non-directive interview, the researcher briefly introduces the topic and then allows the interviewee to express himself/herself freely on the topic (Fenneteau, 2007). The semi-directive interview, on the other hand, is based on an interview guide defined

beforehand and which lists the themes to be addressed during the interview (Evrard, Pras and Roux, 1997). To carry out this study, we opted for the semi-structured interview because this technique allowed us to address all of the themes necessary to achieve the objectives of this study while allowing the interviewees to express themselves freely within each theme.

2.3.2- The field of investigation: Agricultural operations

The field of investigation chosen in this study is the agricultural sector. This choice is motivated by the fact that not only is this sector the feeding breast of humanity, but it is also an important reservoir of employment of several types. As far as the technological future is concerned, it will play an important role in this high potential sector with biofuel and many other energies derived from agricultural waste or its products. To better understand its importance for our country, we have followed the society projects of the nine presidential candidates of October 2018 which all rely on the agricultural sector to solve economic and social problems. This observation strengthened our determination to work on agriculture. The choice of CSR is due to the fact that many studies show that business performance is in most cases achieved if CSR practices are well implemented. With globalization, we cannot remain in autarky. To open up to the world and be competitive with our products, it is imperative that we adhere to international standards. To do this, the agricultural sector, which is our main battle horse, should not escape the integration of CSR practices for greater efficiency and competitiveness. Hence our exploratory study aimed at verifying what representation farmers in Cameroon have of CSR and what practices are implemented in this sector.

2.3.3- Sample Selection

- Sample size

To determine the sample size, we used the saturation criterion. "Saturation is the phenomenon that occurs after a certain period of time in qualitative research when the data collected is no longer new. All efforts to collect new information are therefore rendered useless. In this study, saturation was reached after 13 interviews. In this study, saturation was reached after 13 interviews, which lasted an average of one hour and were conducted in the coastal, central, western, southwestern and southern regions of Cameroon.

- Sample Profile

Our sample is composed of 3 women and 10 men, ranging in age from 23 to 60 years old. 2 are single without children and the other 11 are married men and women and are fathers and mothers of families. The levels of education are spread out from primary school to university level. The lower number of women is not related to misogyny; it is explained by the fact that women do not seem to be the head of the farms, but play a very important role. They are, in fact, the linchpin of many of the farms we visited in situ. Only they play operational roles. The three women we interviewed were mothers, widows, continuing the activity inherited from their husbands to provide for the family. The manager could be an owner, a co-owner or simply a manager of a certain rank responsible for the smooth running of the farm

We want to present below a summary table of the characteristics of the farms and the respondents. At the same time, we will present the duration of the interviews with the thirteen managers. We will use them to calculate the average length of the interviews in order to know if we have remained within the recommendation of Jolibert and Jourdan (2006), i.e. 45 minutes to 1 hour and 30 minutes.

Table 2: Summary table of farm and manager characteristics (Respondents)

CHARACTERISTICS OF HOLDING							CHARACTERISTICS OF MANAGERS (RESPONDENTS)					
companies	Company Code	Number of employes	Main activity	Number of year of existence	Cultivated area (hectares)	Region of location	Repdent's function	Age	Sex	Training	Seniority	Duration of the interviews
1	C.C	22 000	Rubber and palm plantation, tea	71 ans	16 000	South West and North West	HR executive	45-50	M	University	8 year	55 mn
2	P.P	6 600	Banana plantation	33 ans	3 660	Littoral	HR departement	45-50	M	University	7 year	1h05
3	KUI	10	Food crops	6 ans	5	West	Director	55-60	M	Primary	12 year	1h55
4	BIY	15	pineapple	10 ans	6	Littoral	Director	55-60	F	Secondary	4 year	50
5	SOC	6 400	Palmeraie	50 ans	35 000	Littoral	Administrative framework	55-60	H	University	16 year	1h35
6	PRO	13 000	Green bean	26 ans	100	West	Engineer	50-55	H	University	9 year	1h10
7	KON	20	Banana plantation and Cocoa	12 ans	10	West	Director	35-40	H	University	6 year	1h25
8	S.S	7 500	Sugar cane	54 ans	18 700	Center	Administrative framework	40-45	H	University	9 year	1h15
9	BID	11	Various crops	8 ans	8	West	Owner	35-40	H	Secondary	8 year	1h47
10	H.V	10 000	Hévéaculture	43 ans	40 000	South	HR executive	40-45	F	University	15 year old	1h20
11	MDM	15	Cacao +various crops anc cocoa	13 ans	10	Center	Director	40-45	F	Secondary	14 year	1h05
12	ASO	13	Palmeraie	6 ans	10	South west	Manager	35-40	H	Secondary	9 year	52mn
13	APE		Fruit trees	9 ans	20	South	Director	35-40	H	Secondary	9 year	55mn
Total duration of interviews												14,81h
Average duration of interviews = $(55mn+65mn+115mn+50mn+95mn+85mn+75mn+97mn+80mn+65mn+52mn+55mn= 889mn/60) /13=1,13h$ i.e t1h 8mn												889 mn

The average length of the interviews was 1 hour 8 minutes.

- Data collection instrument: the interview protocol

The interviews were conducted using an interview guide (see appendices). The guide is structured around the following theme: 1) Degree of knowledge of CSR by farmers. We wanted to focus our attention strictly on the perception of managers in terms of CSR.

2.3.4.1- The principle of interaction with the subjects studied (farmers)

Creating a favorable interaction between the interviewee and us was not always an easy task. Before starting this fieldwork, with the knowledge we had gained from our reading, we knew that there were important points to respect and pitfalls to avoid. The adaptation to the realities of the field or what some call "the chameleon method" was essential.

2.3.4.2- Listening and questioning

These are two key points to watch out for in order not to fail in the field study. "First of all, you have to know how to listen and observe" (Hlady-Rispal, 2002). In order to successfully collect data, one must avoid "being trapped by one's own ideologies or concerns about reality" (Hlady-Rispal, 2002). For this reason, we avoided having preconceived ideas when conducting our interviews. It is certainly true that the literature and our farm visits had prepared our minds. But the most important thing was to gather the views of the real actors in the field, since it was their perception of CSR that was important. And even then, the literature on this subject was at some points not complete and sometimes not even sufficiently primed to allow us to form a precise idea of the subject at hand.

Listening here becomes an art. In some cases, a lot of patience and self-control was required. We agreed with Hlady-Rispal, 2002, who said: "Listening is also about silences". During the interviews, the respondent, when asked questions, remains silent for a long time. We have learned to give them time, and not to try to fill the silences.

The follow-up questions were used to get the respondent to bounce back and explain his thoughts better. We also used delayed follow-up questions (which return to a point previously mentioned but in an insufficiently thorough manner). These different techniques enabled us to obtain enriching results and a better understanding of the respondents' thoughts.

2.3.4.3- The chameleon method

With this method, the researcher has to adapt to the environment and the personality of the respondents and to their personal anchoring.

"This component seems essential, especially in terms of the data collection technique". (Hlady-Rispal, 2002). At the very beginning of some interviews, particularly in SMEs and especially family farms, there were some signs of reluctance on the part of respondents. Nevertheless, the explanation of the reasons for the recording and the use of the transcripts, the confidentiality affirmed and repeated, and the relationships of trust during our previous visits to the sites, added to the building of trust during the interviews, made it possible to carry out these interviews and to record "free" comments, giving credence to Hlady-Rispal (2002), who cites Van Maanen (1983), who said that "trust is shaped slowly. It emerges in particular contexts when the researcher demonstrates an understanding of the lived reality and a conformity to the forms of understanding of the lived reality and a conformity to the forms of behavior adapted by the people studied". By applying these well-learned rules before embarking on our research, the rate of refusal to be interviewed by the selected individuals illustrates our acceptance by the field.

2.4- Method of data analysis of the qualitative exploratory study

The objective of this section is to present the data analysis method that we used in this qualitative study. The second part will be devoted to the reliability and validity of our study.

2.4.1- Data analysis technique

The interviews we conducted were recorded and transcribed in full. The data collected was then processed through a content analysis. According to Bardin(2009, P.47), content analysis is "a set of communication analysis techniques aiming, through systematic and objective procedures of description of the content of messages, to obtain indicators (quantitative or not) allowing the inference of knowledge related to the conditions of production/reception (inferred variables) of these messages.

First of all, we carried out a "floating" reading of the interviews. This consists of making contact with the analysis documents, getting to know them by letting impressions and orientations come to us (Bardin, 2009).

Next, we conducted a thematic analysis. To do this, we chose the theme as the unit of analysis. We then divided the content of the interviewees' discourse according to the unit of analysis chosen. Finally, we classified the units of analysis into categories defined a priori from previous research. However, some categories emerged during the analysis of the interviews and thus complemented those defined a priori.

This thematic analysis was done vertically and horizontally. The vertical analysis allowed us to see how each interviewee approaches the different themes of the interview guide. The horizontal analysis, on the other hand, allowed us to see how each theme was approached by all the interviewees and to detect regularities.

2.4.2- Reliability and validity of the qualitative study

This sub-section will deal with the reliability and validity of the qualitative study. We will begin with reliability, and then we will address the validity of the study.

- Reliability of the qualitative study

According to authors such as Thétart and Coll (2003), the reliability of qualitative research can be calculated from the results obtained by the same coder who coded the same data in two different periods (inter-coder reliability) or from the results of different coders working on the same data simultaneously (inter-coder reliability).

"Since the process of evaluating inter-coder reliability is particularly long and tedious" (Thiétard and Coll, 2003, P.457), we opted for the first approach. We therefore resumed coding one month after the end of the first coding and did not observe a significant difference in the results obtained.

- Validity of the exploratory study

The validity of qualitative research is difficult to assess because, as Miles and Huberman (1999, p.415) point out, "The problem is that there are no accepted canons, decision rules, algorithms, or even heuristics in qualitative research to indicate whether the findings are valid.

However, precautions were taken to strengthen the validity of this qualitative research:

- First, we pre-tested our interview guide by conducting two interviews that were not included in the data analysis. This pre-test allowed us to rephrase some of the questions in the interview guide that were not understood by the interviewees and to evaluate our interventions.

- Then, as recommended by Yin (1989), we sought to achieve field saturation (data collection continued until the data collected no longer provided new information and the marginal information did not call into question the frameworks constructed) by collecting sufficiently large amounts of data, which led to ensuring the solidity of the data collection.

In this section, we set out the methodology of the exploratory qualitative study that we carried out. During this exploratory study, we conducted individual semi-directive interviews with a sample of 13 people. These interviews, which were recorded and transcribed in their entirety, were then subjected to a horizontal and vertical thematic content analysis. In the following section, we will present the results of this exploratory study.

This time corresponds to the recommendations of Jolibert and Jourdan (2006). According to them, the interviews should be between 45 minutes and 1 hour and 30 minutes long.

2.5- Results of the qualitative exploratory study

The purpose of this subsection is to present the results of the exploratory qualitative study that we conducted. First, we will focus on the representation that Cameroonian farm managers have of CSR as well as the actions implemented with regard to CSR. Then we will highlight, without dwelling too much on it, the obstacles and motivations to the commitment to CSR. Finally, we will outline their thoughts on the effect of the implementation of CSR in the farms on the employees.

2.5.1- Presentation and analysis of cases.

We will be interested in knowing if the farmers know what CSR is, its definition, its practices. Do they know at least one of the aspects, economic, social or environmental?

How do farmers define CSR? What CSR practices are found in farmers? When implementing them, do they always know that they are CSR practices? Do they even have an idea of one of the three components of CSR? What practices are implemented by managers with or without knowledge of CSR? Last but not least, what effect does the implementation of CSR have on employees? This last concern is a breach that we open to know what is the point of view of the leader on this subject that, we will analyze in the second part of this work not without having measured the perception of CSR of the employees.

2.5.1.1- Presentation of results

In this section, we analyze the results of interviews with 13 farm managers in five regions of Cameroon: Central, Southern, Western, Coastal and Southwestern. The sample selected includes both large and small farms. It is clear from the verbatim reports that the views of the farmers are not the same from one farm to another. By making a grouping as indicated in the following box, we will have a clearer vision and will be able to draw a more real and logical conclusion.

Based on these results, we will summarize the opinions on the knowledge of CSR into 4 groups: 1) Managers who have a good knowledge of CSR and apply it knowingly; 2) Managers who have no knowledge of CSR and therefore do not apply it at all; 3) Managers who have no knowledge of CSR but apply its principles without knowing it. 4) Managers who have a good knowledge of CSR, but do not apply it.

Case 1: "... It is the respect of the environment during its current exploitation, and especially its preservation for the good of future generations... ;"

" It is also about ethics in business, especially the respect of commitments, agreements made with stakeholders. It can be towards customers, suppliers, our bankers and especially towards our employees who count enormously for the success of our projects... "

Case 4: "... What are you talking about? SRE? What is SRE? I don't know what you mean. Explain to me no. You are the long pencils right? I haven't been around much huh..."

"...Ah! Good. How do you deal with our employees? At what level? Salaries? Hm! isn't that between us and them? How should I tell you? If they get angry, what do I do? We make the effort to pay! Like they can feed their families with it or take them to the hospital when they are sick, send them to school too, pay for books and notebooks, and give money for doughnuts."

Case 11: "...I don't know how to define this term CSR. But when you quote the words to refresh my memory, I recognize that they are not new to me, on the contrary. We try every day to apply them well among us. We make an effort every month to pay our employees on time. Those who are paid weekly or nightly also have their money programmed before we call them for a job in the plantation.... "

"...We have set up a small mutual insurance company that includes our workers. This mutual not only strengthens our ties, but also allows each other to have small credits at very low rates that help solve problems that our workers and members may have.... "

"We are like members of the same family. This bond forces us to treat each other with respect. Our employees are comfortable and we support each other in times of joy and sorrow.... "

Case 12: "...We don't know what CSR is so what is certain is that we don't apply it in our field. I don't know if our bosses know what it is, but if they do, they've made us apply it without knowing. I'll talk to them about it when we see each other.... "

Case 5: "...I know the principles of CSR well from learning them. The social side is treating your employees well. There is also the economic and environmental aspect. We must protect the environment, not destroy it, but preserve it for our children who will also need it tomorrow. Ha! I almost forgot the ethics in business..."

"...If I open our CSR manuals, I will quote a lot of things about good working conditions, fair pay, proximity to employees, social protection, social dialogue, The little that is applied is just for controls; It's smoke and mirrors. It's like

a make-up that makes the woman different, therefore beautiful, for the time of an outing and then she becomes herself again. So it's just cosmetics as one author says...We take care of the quality of the products.

Table3: Summary of results from farm manager interviews

1- Knowledge of CSR

Managers who have a good knowledge of CSR and apply it with full knowledge of the facts (pragmatic managers)

- Case 1: CC
- Case 2: PA
- Case 3: KUI
- Case 6: PRO
- Case 7: KON
- Case 8: SS
- Case 10: HV

Managers who have no knowledge of CSR and therefore do not apply it (lay managers)

- Case 4: BIY
- Case 9: BID

Leaders who have no knowledge of CSR but apply it without knowing it (Altruistic leaders)

- Case 13: APE Case 12: ASO
- Case 11: MDM

Managers who have a good knowledge of CSR, but do not apply it (deviant managers)

- Case 5: SOC

Sources: Our care

2.5.1.2- Analysis of results

We note in these results that the majority of leaders, 8 representing 62% of leaders, have a good knowledge of CSR and give a definition consistent with those generally accepted. This result is in line with those of Zouhair Laaraf (2010).

Only 38% of managers do not know what CSR is (Moskolai, 2016). Nevertheless, among these managers, 23% of them implement some CSR principles in their operations without knowing it. This result corroborates the studies of Youcef (2013). CSR in these farms is not formalized (Fotso sangué, 2018). These results allow us to join Leila Ben Hassine and Chiraz Ghozzi-Nekheli (2013) for whom personal conviction and culture influence the commitment to CSR. 1% of our sample is strikingly similar to the reluctant (Moskolai, 2016).

It is clear from this qualitative study that leaders' perception of CSR also depends on the sector of activity (Moskolai, 2016). Our analysis allows us to join (Wong and Yaméogo, 2011) who believe that research on the perception of leaders must necessarily take into account the African cultural and economic context.

Overall, on farms in Cameroon, managers are aware of CSR and are implementing CSR practices within their production units. The majority of employees, if not all, are aware of the merits of CSR, as its practices affect them positively. They contribute to their development and well-being in their work environment and beyond, in their families. However, it should be noted that this result is linked to the opinions of managers, which should not necessarily be taken at face value. This opinion could be biased.

From these results, we can identify 4 types of farm managers according to their degree of knowledge of CSR:

- 1- Pragmatic leaders: They have a good knowledge of CSR and apply it with full knowledge of the facts
- 2- The lay managers: They have no knowledge of CSR and therefore do not apply it.

3- Altruistic Leaders: These have no knowledge of CSR but apply it without knowing it.

4- Deviant Leaders: They have a good knowledge of CSR, but do not apply it.

3- Implications

The objective of this research was to understand the perception of farm managers of CSR in Cameroon. To achieve this, we mobilized qualitative research, specifically an exploratory empirical survey based on case studies of 13 farm managers based in Cameroon. According to the typology of enterprises in Cameroon, the farms surveyed are in some cases large, and in others small and medium-sized. The actors' discourse allowed us to identify 4 types of leaders: 7 pragmatic leaders who have a good knowledge of CSR and implement it with full knowledge of the facts; 2 lay leaders who have no knowledge of CSR and therefore do not apply it; 3 of the respondents are altruistic and therefore have no knowledge of CSR but apply it without knowing it; Finally, we found in the speeches, 1 deviant leader who has a good knowledge of CSR, but does not apply it. The social aspect of CSR is the one that comes up the most in the discourse of the actors. This is justified by a reality that is catching up with this sector: its greed for the land necessary for the extension of exploitable agricultural spaces. The environmental component only exists in the companies' diaries and is in fact only cosmetic. (Martinet and Payaux, 2008)

On a theoretical level, this research will help enrich knowledge on CSR and its perception in a sector that is vital for humanity and deserves to be questioned (Ramonet, 2003) given the actions of humans in search of resources necessary for its survival. Their actions on a planetary scale are reflected in the reduction of biological biodiversity, the scarcity of certain resources and an increase and globalization of air, water and soil pollution (Delchet, 2003). We have taken into account, which is not common, the managers of large, small and medium-sized farms in this research work. This allowed us to take into account the specificities of small and medium-sized farms. It also allowed us to observe the reality of the perception of managers of all types and to take a comparative approach that could be the subject of a future study.

From a managerial perspective, this research has allowed us to better understand what farm managers think about CSR and why they implement or do not implement CSR on their farms. Thus, we recommend that farm managers with no knowledge of CSR seek to understand the important role it plays in business performance today. To those who implemented it without knowing it well, to continue in the same way while getting closer to competent experts in the field or to the ministry of supervision which will be of great help to them in mastering the techniques that can help to make good use of it for a better future of their farms. To the public authorities, we recommend to set up incentive measures that can encourage companies, especially small ones (more numerous) to adopt responsible behaviors. It should also set up training programs for managers who want to learn more about CSR. Popularization of this topic could be done on radio and television channels. Community radio stations could do this in the vernacular of each region of operation to help managers who do not easily use French and English.

The results of this research must take into account certain limitations. These results are not easily generalized, given that we only interviewed 13 managers and this only in 5 regions of Cameroon. Although we are aware of this methodological limitation, the main objective was to understand the perception of farm managers with regard to CSR and thereby draw the attention of researchers to a topical issue with high stakes for African businesses. Also, we plan in future research to study the perception of employees of CSR which is according to Igalens and Tahri, (2012) "the new HRM". We could also continue this research by taking into account several sectors of activity.

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